

See discussions, stats, and author profiles for this publication at: <https://www.researchgate.net/publication/351056031>

Observation of Strong Valley Magnetic Response in Monolayer Transition Metal Dichalcogenide Alloys of $\text{Mo}_{0.5}\text{W}_{0.5}\text{Se}_2$ and $\text{Mo}_{0.5}\text{W}_{0.5}\text{Se}_2/\text{WS}_2$ Heterostructures

Article in ACS Nano · April 2021

DOI: 10.1021/acsnano.0c10478

CITATIONS

4

READS

145

16 authors, including:

C. X. Cong

Fudan University

167 PUBLICATIONS 9,059 CITATIONS

SEE PROFILE

Yang Weihuang

Hangzhou Dianzi University

56 PUBLICATIONS 1,673 CITATIONS

SEE PROFILE

Thu Ha Do

Agency for Science, Technology and Research (A*STAR)

14 PUBLICATIONS 527 CITATIONS

SEE PROFILE

Shun Feng

Heriot-Watt University

16 PUBLICATIONS 322 CITATIONS

SEE PROFILE

Some of the authors of this publication are also working on these related projects:

Two Dimensional Materials [View project](#)

nanocatalysis [View project](#)

Observation of strong valley magnetic response in monolayer transition metal dichalcogenide alloys of $\text{Mo}_{0.5}\text{W}_{0.5}\text{Se}_2$ and $\text{Mo}_{0.5}\text{W}_{0.5}\text{Se}_2/\text{WS}_2$ heterostructure

Lishu Wu[†], Chunxiao Cong^{‡,}, Weihuang Yang[§], Yu Chen^{†,||}, Yan Shao[⊥], T. Thu Ha Do[†], Wen Wen[†], Shun Feng^{†,§}, Chenji Zou[†], Hongbo Zhang[†], Bowen Du[†], Bingchen Cao[†], Jingzhi Shang^{#,*}, Qihua Xiong[†], Kian Ping Loh[⊥], and Ting Yu^{†,*}*

[†]Division of Physics and Applied Physics, School of Physical and Mathematical Sciences, Nanyang Technological University, Singapore 637371, Singapore

[‡]State Key Laboratory of ASIC and System, School of Information Science and Technology, Fudan University, Shanghai 200433, P. R. China

[§]Key Laboratory of RF Circuits and System of Ministry of Education, Hangzhou Dianzi University, Hangzhou 310018, Zhejiang, P. R. China

[⊥]Department of Chemistry, National University of Singapore, Singapore 117543, Singapore

[#]Xi'an Institute of Flexible Electronics, Northwestern Polytechnical University, Xi'an 710072, Shaanxi, P. R. China

KEYWORDS: Transition metal dichalcogenide alloys, Van der Waals heterostructures, Interlayer coupling, Valley Zeeman splitting, Photoluminescence

ABSTRACT: Monolayer (1L) transition metal dichalcogenide (TMD) alloys have emerged as a new material system towards future applications for electronic, optoelectronic and spintronic devices owing to their tunable electronic structures, effective masses of carriers and valley polarization with various alloy compositions. Particularly, the unique valley physics associated with valley polarization and Zeeman effect opens new opportunities for valleytronic applications based on 1L TMDs and their alloys. However, valley magnetic response in 1L TMD alloys largely remains unexplored. Here, we report strong valley magnetic response of negatively charged excitons (trions) in $\text{Mo}_{0.5}\text{W}_{0.5}\text{Se}_2$ and $\text{Mo}_{0.5}\text{W}_{0.5}\text{Se}_2/\text{WS}_2$ heterostructures investigated by cryogenic magneto-photoluminescence microspectroscopy. The large g -factors have been extracted for $\text{Mo}_{0.5}\text{W}_{0.5}\text{Se}_2$ and $\text{Mo}_{0.5}\text{W}_{0.5}\text{Se}_2/\text{WS}_2$, respectively, which are attributed to the significant impact of strong Coulomb interactions on the trion emission under a perpendicular magnetic field. The slight reduction of the valley Zeeman splitting in the heterostructure of $\text{Mo}_{0.5}\text{W}_{0.5}\text{Se}_2/\text{WS}_2$ is explained in terms of the doping variation caused by the interlayer charge transfer between $\text{Mo}_{0.5}\text{W}_{0.5}\text{Se}_2$ and WS_2 , which agrees well with our density functional theory calculations of the band alignment in the $\text{Mo}_{0.5}\text{W}_{0.5}\text{Se}_2/\text{WS}_2$ heterostructure. Our findings give new insights into the optical properties of 1L TMD alloys and the interlayer coupling between TMD alloys and TMDs, which will shed light on the development of valleytronic applications.

Monolayer (1L) group-VI transition metal dichalcogenides (TMDs) of MX_2 ($M = \text{Mo}$ or W ; $X = \text{S}$ or Se)¹⁻⁴, have aroused great interest due to their novel properties of direct band gaps⁵ and extra valley degree of freedom⁶⁻⁷ and become the very promising two-dimensional (2D) semiconducting and valleytronic⁸⁻¹⁰ materials. Recently, TMD alloys¹¹ have been created by mixing either transition metals ($\text{Mo}_{1-x}\text{W}_x\text{X}_2$) or chalcogen atoms ($\text{MS}_{2-x}\text{Se}_{2-2x}$) ($x = 0 \sim 1$) to enrich electronic and optical properties of the 2D TMD family, which are also good candidates for electronic, optoelectronic and valleytronic applications.¹¹⁻¹² More importantly, the band gaps of TMD alloys can be continuously modulated with the compositions, bridging of the energy gaps left by classic TMDs (*i.e.* MX_2) and thus covering a broad emission range from visible to near infrared.^{11, 13-19} Particularly, the composition-tunable electronic structures allow to control the type-II band alignment formed in $\text{WS}_2/\text{WS}_{2(1-x)}\text{Se}_{2x}$ lateral heterostructures.²⁰ Furthermore, the tunable composition is also beneficial to manipulate the spin-splitting energies of conduction and valence bands, for example, ΔE_{VB} equals to about 200 ~ 425 meV when x varies from 0 to 1 in the case of $\text{Mo}_{1-x}\text{W}_x\text{Se}_2$ ¹², and to control the valley polarization degrees such as 0 ~ 40 % for $\text{Mo}_{1-x}\text{W}_x\text{Se}_2$ ¹² and 60 % for $\text{WS}_{0.6}\text{Se}_{1.4}$ ²¹. These tunable optical bandgaps together with the spin-valley coupling make 1L TMD alloys and their heterostructures attractive for studies on novel valley physics. However, as one of critical concerns in valleytronic applications, the effects of magnetic field on valley degeneracy lifting of TMD alloys remain unexplored.

In this work, we demonstrate strong valley magnetic response in 1L TMD alloys of $\text{Mo}_{0.5}\text{W}_{0.5}\text{Se}_2$ and its van der Waals heterostructure of $\text{Mo}_{0.5}\text{W}_{0.5}\text{Se}_2/\text{WS}_2$. Magneto-photoluminescence (PL) studies of 1L $\text{Mo}_{0.5}\text{W}_{0.5}\text{Se}_2$ alloy show the robust valley Zeeman splitting of the negatively charged exciton or trion (X_A^-), correlated to strong Coulomb interactions. Moreover, the g -factor slightly weakening in $\text{Mo}_{0.5}\text{W}_{0.5}\text{Se}_2/\text{WS}_2$ is associated with the interlayer

charge transfer between $\text{Mo}_{0.5}\text{W}_{0.5}\text{Se}_2$ and WS_2 , agreeing well with the DFT calculations of the band alignment of $\text{Mo}_{0.5}\text{W}_{0.5}\text{Se}_2/\text{WS}_2$ heterostructures. Our findings will be of benefit to the development of practical devices based on TMD alloys and their type-II heterostructures.

Results and Discussion

Recent studies²¹⁻²³ have shown that the hBN crystals are wide band-gap insulators with atomically smooth surfaces, thus preparing TMD alloys on them will be more helpful to study optical properties of TMD alloys, compared to those on SiO_2/Si substrates. Here, we fabricated $\text{Mo}_{0.5}\text{W}_{0.5}\text{Se}_2/\text{WS}_2$ heterostructures on hBN through a modified PDMS-based dry transfer technique (see Figure S1). Figure 1(a) presents the schematic of a hybrid $\text{Mo}_{0.5}\text{W}_{0.5}\text{Se}_2/\text{WS}_2$ sample encapsulated by hBN and its optical image is shown in Figure 1(b). As reported¹¹, 1L TMD alloys exhibit tunable emission energies between the optical bandgaps of two binary counterparts (*i.e.* MX_2). For example, 1L $\text{Mo}_{0.5}\text{W}_{0.5}\text{Se}_2$ alloy has a direct optical bandgap at + K and – K corners in the first Brillouin zone with the emission photon energy sitting between the ones of 1L MoSe_2 and WSe_2 .^{18,24} Referring to the previously reported band alignments of type-II TMD heterostructures²⁵⁻²⁶, we schematically illustrate the energy-level diagram of $\text{Mo}_{0.5}\text{W}_{0.5}\text{Se}_2/\text{WS}_2$ heterostructures in Figure 1(c), in which the conduction band minimum (CBM) and valence band maximum (VBM) around the K point are located at 1L WS_2 and $\text{Mo}_{0.5}\text{W}_{0.5}\text{Se}_2$, respectively, and the electron (hole) transfers from the conduction (valence) band edge of 1L $\text{Mo}_{0.5}\text{W}_{0.5}\text{Se}_2$ (WS_2) to 1L WS_2 ($\text{Mo}_{0.5}\text{W}_{0.5}\text{Se}_2$). Note that, such a type-II alignment is further confirmed by our theoretical calculations of electronic structures, which will be discussed later.

PL and Raman measurements of 1L $\text{Mo}_{0.5}\text{W}_{0.5}\text{Se}_2$ alloy and the $\text{Mo}_{0.5}\text{W}_{0.5}\text{Se}_2/\text{WS}_2$ heterostructure were conducted at 4.2 K with an excitation laser at 532 nm under a low power to

prevent unexpected thermal effects unless stated otherwise. Figures 1(d) and 1(e) present Raman and PL spectra of the samples, respectively, where the signals are collected from 1L WS₂, 1L Mo_{0.5}W_{0.5}Se₂ and Mo_{0.5}W_{0.5}Se₂/WS₂ heterobilayers as indicated in orange, green, and blue lines, individually. On the one hand, in Figure 1(d), the pristine 1L WS₂ region noticeably exhibits E_{2g}-dominated²⁷⁻²⁸ and A_{1g} modes at 359.9 and 421.0 cm⁻¹, respectively, of which, the difference in the frequency is about 61 cm⁻¹; the pristine 1L Mo_{0.5}W_{0.5}Se₂ shows a A_{1g}-dominated peak at 250.3 cm⁻¹, consistent with the previous reports²⁴.

On the other hand, as seen in Figure 1(e), the PL spectrum of pristine 1L WS₂ is composed of a neutral exciton peak and a broad localized emission band around 2.09 and 2.00 eV, respectively. Meanwhile, one emission band of the pristine 1L Mo_{0.5}W_{0.5}Se₂ was observed at about 1.68 eV, which is within the spectral range of exciton and trion bands of 1L Mo_{1-x}W_xSe₂ alloy ($x = 0.5$) according to the previous studies^{12,34}.

To further examine the excitonic nature of 1L Mo_{0.5}W_{0.5}Se₂, we conducted the excitation power-dependent PL measurements. Figure 2(a) presents the color plot of the PL spectra as a function of laser excitation power of the Mo_{0.5}W_{0.5}Se₂. The corresponding PL spectra under varied excitation powers are shown in Figure S3. Figures 2(b), 2(c) and 2(d) show the extracted integrated intensity, position and FWHM of the peak as functions of laser excitation power, respectively, in which the integrated intensity increases linearly with the laser power while the peak position and the FWHM keep almost unchanged. Hence, the excitation-dependent PL behaviors indicate the peak does not originate from the defect states typically resulting in a sublinear dependence⁴¹; in combination with the observed large and doping-sensitive Zeeman splitting later, the peak is consequently confirmed to be the trion dominated emission of 1L Mo_{0.5}W_{0.5}Se₂ alloy. To eliminate the possible environmental influence and further address the intrinsic optical properties of TMD

alloy, we add a capping layer of hBN on 1L Mo_{0.5}W_{0.5}Se₂/hBN and compare the Raman and PL spectral features of 1L Mo_{0.5}W_{0.5}Se₂/hBN and hBN/1L Mo_{0.5}W_{0.5}Se₂/hBN. However, the one is located at about 1.7 eV for the hBN-encapsulated one.

To study the valley magnetic response in 1L Mo_{0.5}W_{0.5}Se₂ and the Mo_{0.5}W_{0.5}Se₂/WS₂ heterostructure, magneto-PL measurements were carried out. Figures 3(a) and 3(b) present the color maps of normalized PL spectra of the 1L Mo_{0.5}W_{0.5}Se₂ alloy sandwiched by hBN layers as a function of magnetic field (\mathbf{B}) under the left circular (σ^-) excitation and σ^- detection, and the right circular (σ^+) excitation and σ^+ detection, respectively. Figure 3(d) displays the valley splitting energy versus \mathbf{B} field, in which the slope of about 0.48 meV/T and the g -factor of 8.3 ± 0.2 are obtained. Figure 4 presents the magneto-PL studies of TMD alloy based heterostructure of Mo_{0.5}W_{0.5}Se₂/WS₂ sandwiched by hBN layers. Contour plots of the normalized PL intensities of the trion emission from the Mo_{0.5}W_{0.5}Se₂ component as functions of the photon energy and \mathbf{B} field under the $\sigma^+\sigma^+$ and $\sigma^-\sigma^-$ configurations are illustrated in Figures 4(a) and 4(b), respectively. The peak positions for $\sigma^+\sigma^+$ and $\sigma^-\sigma^-$, and the Zeeman splitting energy as functions of \mathbf{B} field are shown in Figures 4(c) and 4(d), respectively. The Zeeman splitting energy versus \mathbf{B} field is fitted by the linear function with a slope of 0.41 meV/T, resulting in a g -factor of 7.1 ± 0.2 , which is smaller than that of hBN/Mo_{0.5}W_{0.5}Se₂/hBN.

Conclusions

To sum up, we have investigated the valley Zeeman effect of Mo_{0.5}W_{0.5}Se₂ and the Mo_{0.5}W_{0.5}Se₂/WS₂ heterostructure by cryogenic magneto-PL micro-spectroscopy. The charged excitonic emission is dominant for the low-temperature spectral features of 1L Mo_{0.5}W_{0.5}Se₂. By scanning the out-of-plane magnetic field from -7 to 7 T, we obtained the large g factor of 8.3 for

$\text{Mo}_{0.5}\text{W}_{0.5}\text{Se}_2$, which is attributed to the strong Coulomb-interactions induced trion energy shifts. Furthermore, the strong interlayer coupling in the $\text{Mo}_{0.5}\text{W}_{0.5}\text{Se}_2/\text{WS}_2$ heterostructure was found, which was revealed by Raman and PL features together with the varied valley magnetic response. The slight weakening of magnetic response of 1L $\text{Mo}_{0.5}\text{W}_{0.5}\text{Se}_2$ in the heterostructure (*i.e.* the g factor of 7.1) referring to that of the pristine 1L $\text{Mo}_{0.5}\text{W}_{0.5}\text{Se}_2$, is attributed to the charge transfer due to the formation of the type-II band alignment, which is supported by our DFT calculations of the electronic band structures of $\text{Mo}_{0.5}\text{W}_{0.5}\text{Se}_2/\text{WS}_2$. Our findings open many opportunities for developing valleytronic applications based on the newly emerged TMD alloys and their heterostructures.

AUTHOR INFORMATION

Corresponding Author

*yuting@ntu.edu.sg

*cxcong@fudan.edu.cn

*iamjzshang@nwpu.edu.cn

Notes

The authors declare no competing financial interests.

ACKNOWLEDGMENT

This project is mainly supported by the Academic Research Fund Tier 1 (RG93/19), the Ministry of Education of Singapore Tier 2 (MOE2019-T2-1-044 and MOE2018-T2-2-072), and the Singapore National Research Foundation (NRF) under the Competitive Research Programs (NRF-CRP-21-2018-0007). C.C. thanks the support of the Shanghai Municipal Natural Science Foundation (No. 16ZR1402500), Shanghai Municipal Science and Technology Commission

(Grant No. 18JC1410300), National Young 1000 Talent Plan of China, and the National Natural Science Foundation of China (No. 61774040). This project is also supported by National Natural Science Foundation of China (No. 11774170). W.Y. acknowledges the support of the National Natural Science Foundation of China (No. 61704040) and Zhejiang Provincial Natural Science Foundation of China under Grant No. LGG19F040003. J.S. appreciates the support of the Fundamental Research Funds for the Central Universities of China, National Natural Science Foundation of China under Grant No. 61904151, Natural Science Foundation of Shaanxi under Grant No. 2020JM-108 and the Joint Research Funds of Department of Science & Technology of Shaanxi Province and Northwestern Polytechnical University (No. 2020GXLH-Z-020). K.P.L. would like to acknowledge the National research foundation grant NRF-CRP22-2019-0006, Prime Minister's Office, Singapore. S.F. thanks the support by H2020-MSCA-IF-2020 project SingExTr (No. 101031596).

REFERENCES

1. Mak, K. F.; Shan, J., Opportunities and challenges of interlayer exciton control and manipulation. *Nat. Nanotechnol.* **2018**, 13, 974-976.
2. Rivera, P.; Yu, H.; Seyler, K. L.; Wilson, N. P.; Yao, W.; Xu, X., Interlayer valley excitons in heterobilayers of transition metal dichalcogenides. *Nat. Nanotechnol.* **2018**, 13, 1004-1015.
3. Cong, C.; Shang, J.; Wang, Y.; Yu, T., Optical Properties of 2D Semiconductor WS₂. *Adv. Opt. Mater.* **2018**, 6, 1700767.
4. Shang, J.; Cong, C.; Wu, L.; Huang, W.; Yu, T., Light Sources and Photodetectors Enabled by 2D Semiconductors. *Small Methods* **2018**, 2, 1800019.
5. Duan, X.; Wang, C.; Pan, A.; Yu, R.; Duan, X., Two-dimensional transition metal dichalcogenides as atomically thin semiconductors: opportunities and challenges. *Chem. Soc. Rev.*

2015, 44, 8859-8876.

6. Zeng, H.; Dai, J.; Yao, W.; Xiao, D.; Cui, X., Valley polarization in MoS₂ monolayers by optical pumping. *Nat. Nanotechnol.* **2012**, 7, 490.
7. Feng, S.; Cong, C.; Konabe, S.; Zhang, J.; Shang, J.; Chen, Y.; Zou, C.; Cao, B.; Wu, L.; Peimyoo, N.; Zhang, B.; Yu, T., Engineering Valley Polarization of Monolayer WS₂: A Physical Doping Approach. *Small* **2019**, 15, 1805503.
8. Aivazian, G.; Gong, Z. R.; Jones, A. M.; Chu, R. L.; Yan, J.; Mandrus, D. G.; Zhang, C. W.; Cobden, D.; Yao, W.; Xu, X., Magnetic control of valley pseudospin in monolayer WSe₂. *Nat. Phys.* **2015**, 11, 148-152.
9. Xu, X. D.; Yao, W.; Xiao, D.; Heinz, T. F., Spin and pseudospins in layered transition metal dichalcogenides. *Nat. Phys.* **2014**, 10, 343-350.
10. Schaibley, J. R.; Yu, H.; Clark, G.; Rivera, P.; Ross, J. S.; Seyler, K. L.; Yao, W.; Xu, X., Valleytronics in 2D materials. *Nat. Rev. Mater.* **2016**, 1, 16055.
11. Xie, L. M., Two-dimensional transition metal dichalcogenide alloys: preparation, characterization and applications. *Nanoscale* **2015**, 7, 18392-18401.
12. Wang, G.; Robert, C.; Suslu, A.; Chen, B.; Yang, S. J.; Alamdari, S.; Gerber, I. C.; Amand, T.; Marie, X.; Tongay, S.; Urbaszek, B., Spin-orbit engineering in transition metal dichalcogenide alloy monolayers. *Nat. Commun.* **2015**, 6, 10110.
13. Taghinejad, H.; Eftekhar, A. A.; Campbell, P. M.; Beatty, B.; Taghinejad, M.; Zhou, Y.; Perini, C. J.; Moradinejad, H.; Henderson, W. E.; Woods, E. V.; Zhang, X.; Ajayan, P.; Reed, E. J.; Vogel, E. M.; Adibi, A., Strain relaxation via formation of cracks in compositionally modulated two-dimensional semiconductor alloys. *npj. 2D Mater. Appl.* **2018**, 2, 10.
14. Duan, X. D.; Wang, C.; Fan, Z.; Hao, G. L.; Kou, L. Z.; Halim, U.; Li, H. L.; Wu, X. P.;

- Wang, Y. C.; Jiang, J. H.; Pan, A. L.; Huang, Y.; Yu, R. Q.; Duan, X. F., Synthesis of $WS_{2x}Se_{2-2x}$ Alloy Nanosheets with Composition-Tunable Electronic Properties. *Nano Lett.* **2016**, 16, 264-269.
15. Chen, Y. F.; Xi, J. Y.; Dumcenco, D. O.; Liu, Z.; Suenaga, K.; Wang, D.; Shuai, Z. G.; Huang, Y. S.; Xie, L. M., Tunable Band Gap Photoluminescence from Atomically Thin Transition-Metal Dichalcogenide Alloys. *ACS Nano* **2013**, 7, 4610-4616.
16. Feng, Q.; Zhu, Y.; Hong, J.; Zhang, M.; Duan, W.; Mao, N.; Wu, J.; Xu, H.; Dong, F.; Lin, F.; Jin, C.; Wang, C.; Zhang, J.; Xie, L., Growth of Large-Area 2D $MoS_{2(1-x)}Se_{2x}$ Semiconductor Alloys. *Adv. Mater.* **2014**, 26, 2648-2653.
17. Li, H. L.; Duan, X. D.; Wu, X. P.; Zhuang, X. J.; Zhou, H.; Zhang, Q. L.; Zhu, X. L.; Hu, W.; Ren, P. Y.; Guo, P. F.; Ma, L.; Fan, X. P.; Wang, X. X.; Xu, J. Y.; Pan, A. L.; Duan, X. F., Growth of Alloy $MoS_{2x}Se_{2(1-x)}$ Nanosheets with Fully Tunable Chemical Compositions and Optical Properties. *J. Am. Chem. Soc.* **2014**, 136, 3756-3759.
18. Huang, B.; Yoon, M.; Sumpter, B. G.; Wei, S. H.; Liu, F., Alloy Engineering of Defect Properties in Semiconductors: Suppression of Deep Levels in Transition-Metal Dichalcogenides. *Phys. Rev. Lett.* **2015**, 115, 126806.
19. Chen, Y.; Dumcenco, D. O.; Zhu, Y.; Zhang, X.; Mao, N.; Feng, Q.; Zhang, M.; Zhang, J.; Tan, P.-H.; Huang, Y.-S.; Xie, L., Composition-dependent Raman modes of $Mo_{1-x}W_xS_2$ monolayer alloys. *Nanoscale* **2014**, 6, 2833-2839.
20. Zheng, B. Y.; Ma, C.; Li, D.; Lan, J. Y.; Zhang, Z.; Sun, X. X.; Zheng, W. H.; Yang, T. F.; Zhu, C. G.; Ouyang, G.; Xu, G. Z.; Zhu, X. L.; Wang, X.; Pan, A. L., Band Alignment Engineering in Two-Dimensional Lateral Heterostructures. *J. Am. Chem. Soc.* **2018**, 140, 11193-11197.
21. Meng, Y. Z.; Wang, T. M.; Li, Z. P.; Qin, Y.; Lian, Z.; Chen, Y. W.; Lucking, M. C.; Beach, K.; Taniguchi, T.; Watanabe, K.; Tongay, S.; Song, F. Q.; Terrones, H.; Shi, S. F., Excitonic

Complexes and Emerging Interlayer Electron-Phonon Coupling in BN Encapsulated Monolayer Semiconductor Alloy: $WS_{0.6}Se_{1.4}$. *Nano Lett.* **2019**, 19, 299-307.

22. Cadiz, F.; Courtade, E.; Robert, C.; Wang, G.; Shen, Y.; Cai, H.; Taniguchi, T.; Watanabe, K.; Carrere, H.; Lagarde, D.; Manca, M.; Amand, T.; Renucci, P.; Tongay, S.; Marie, X.; Urbaszek, B., Excitonic Linewidth Approaching the Homogeneous Limit in MoS_2 -Based van der Waals Heterostructures. *Phys. Rev. X* **2017**, 7, 021026.

23. Cong, C.; Zou, C.; Cao, B.; Wu, L.; Shang, J.; Wang, H.; Qiu, Z.; Hu, L.; Tian, P.; Liu, R.; Yu, T., Intrinsic excitonic emission and valley Zeeman splitting in epitaxial MS_2 ($M = Mo$ and W) monolayers on hexagonal boron nitride. *Nano Res.* **2018**, 11, 6227-6236.

24. Zhang, M.; Wu, J. X.; Zhu, Y. M.; Dumcenco, D. O.; Hong, J. H.; Mao, N. N.; Deng, S. B.; Chen, Y. F.; Yang, Y. L.; Jin, C. H.; Chaki, S. H.; Huang, Y. S.; Zhang, J.; Xie, L. M., Two-Dimensional Molybdenum Tungsten Diselenide Alloys: Photoluminescence, Raman Scattering, and Electrical Transport. *ACS Nano* **2014**, 8, 7130-7137.

25. Kang, J.; Tongay, S.; Zhou, J.; Li, J. B.; Wu, J. Q., Band offsets and heterostructures of two-dimensional semiconductors. *Appl. Phys. Lett.* **2013**, 102, 012111.

26. Gong, C.; Zhang, H. J.; Wang, W. H.; Colombo, L.; Wallace, R. M.; Cho, K. J., Band alignment of two-dimensional transition metal dichalcogenides: Application in tunnel field effect transistors. *Appl. Phys. Lett.* **2013**, 103, 053513.

27. Mitioglu, A. A.; Plochocka, P.; Deligeorgis, G.; Anghel, S.; Kulyuk, L.; Maude, D. K., Second-order resonant Raman scattering in single-layer tungsten disulfide WS_2 . *Phys. Rev. B* **2014**, 89, 245442.

28. Kumar, P.; Singh, B.; Kumar, P.; Balakrishnan, V., Competing thermal expansion mismatch and lattice strain engineered growth of crack free WS_2 in-plane heterostructures. *J. Mater. Chem.*

C **2018**, 6, 11407-11415.

29. Chiu, M.-H.; Li, M.-Y.; Zhang, W.; Hsu, W.-T.; Chang, W.-H.; Terrones, M.; Terrones, H.; Li, L.-J., Spectroscopic Signatures for Interlayer Coupling in MoS₂-WSe₂ van der Waals Stacking. *ACS Nano* **2014**, 8, 9649-9656.

30. Li, M.-Y.; Chen, C.-H.; Shi, Y.; Li, L.-J., Heterostructures based on two-dimensional layered materials and their potential applications. *Mater. Today* **2016**, 19, 322-335.

31. Wang, Y.; Cong, C.; Yang, W.; Shang, J.; Peimyoo, N.; Chen, Y.; Kang, J.; Wang, J.; Huang, W.; Yu, T., Strain-induced direct–indirect bandgap transition and phonon modulation in monolayer WS₂. *Nano Res.* **2015**, 8, 2562-2572.

32. Chakraborty, B.; Bera, A.; Muthu, D. V. S.; Bhowmick, S.; Waghmare, U. V.; Sood, A. K., Symmetry-dependent phonon renormalization in monolayer MoS₂ transistor. *Phys. Rev. B* **2012**, 85, 161403.

33. Huang, S.; Ling, X.; Liang, L.; Kong, J.; Terrones, H.; Meunier, V.; Dresselhaus, M. S., Probing the Interlayer Coupling of Twisted Bilayer MoS₂ Using Photoluminescence Spectroscopy. *Nano Lett.* **2014**, 14, 5500-5508.

34. Ye, J. L.; Niu, B. H.; Li, Y.; Li, T.; Zhang, X. H., Exciton valley dynamics in monolayer Mo_{1-x}W_xSe₂ ($x = 0, 0.5, 1$). *Appl. Phys. Lett.* **2017**, 111, 152106.

35. Hong, X. P.; Kim, J.; Shi, S. F.; Zhang, Y.; Jin, C. H.; Sun, Y. H.; Tongay, S.; Wu, J. Q.; Zhang, Y. F.; Wang, F., Ultrafast charge transfer in atomically thin MoS₂/WS₂ heterostructures. *Nat. Nanotechnol.* **2014**, 9, 682-686.

36. Rivera, P.; Schaibley, J. R.; Jones, A. M.; Ross, J. S.; Wu, S. F.; Aivazian, G.; Klement, P.; Seyler, K.; Clark, G.; Ghimire, N. J.; Yan, J. Q.; Mandrus, D. G.; Yao, W.; Xu, X. D., Observation of long-lived interlayer excitons in monolayer MoSe₂-WSe₂ heterostructures. *Nat. Commun.* **2015**,

6, 6242.

37. Tran, K.; Moody, G.; Wu, F. C.; Lu, X. B.; Choi, J.; Kim, K.; Rai, A.; Sanchez, D. A.; Quan, J. M.; Singh, A.; Embley, J.; Zepeda, A.; Campbell, M.; Autry, T.; Taniguchi, T.; Watanabe, K.; Lu, N. S.; Banerjee, S. K.; Silverman, K. L.; Kim, S.; Tutuc, E.; Yang, L.; MacDonald, A. H.; Li, X. Q., Evidence for moire excitons in van der Waals heterostructures. *Nature* **2019**, *567*, 71-75.

38. Zhu, B. R.; Chen, X.; Cui, X. D., Exciton Binding Energy of Monolayer WS₂. *Sci. Rep.* **2015**, *5*, 9218.

39. Chernikov, A.; van der Zande, A. M.; Hill, H. M.; Rigosi, A. F.; Velauthapillai, A.; Hone, J.; Heinz, T. F., Electrical Tuning of Exciton Binding Energies in Monolayer WS₂. *Phys. Rev. Lett.* **2015**, *115*, 126802.

40. Shang, J. Z.; Shen, X. N.; Cong, C. X.; Peimyoo, N.; Cao, B. C.; Eginligil, M.; Yu, T., Observation of Excitonic Fine Structure in a 2D Transition-Metal Dichalcogenide Semiconductor. *ACS Nano* **2015**, *9*, 647-655.

41. Tongay, S.; Suh, J.; Ataca, C.; Fan, W.; Luce, A.; Kang, J. S.; Liu, J.; Ko, C.; Raghunathan, R.; Zhou, J.; Ogletree, F.; Li, J. B.; Grossman, J. C.; Wu, J. Q., Defects activated photoluminescence in two-dimensional semiconductors: interplay between bound, charged, and free excitons. *Sci. Rep.* **2013**, *3*, 2657.

42. Florian, M.; Hartmann, M.; Steinhoff, A.; Klein, J.; Holleitner, A. W.; Finley, J. J.; Wehling, T. O.; Kaniber, M.; Gies, C., The Dielectric Impact of Layer Distances on Exciton and Trion Binding Energies in van der Waals Heterostructures. *Nano Lett.* **2018**, *18*, 2725-2732.

43. Eric W. M., J. H., Hanna G. R., Eunice P., Michael-Henr W., Hui D., Steven T. C., Encapsulation Narrows Excitonic Homogeneous Linewidth of Exfoliated MoSe₂ Monolayer. *arXiv:1810.09834*.

44. Wierzbowski, J.; Klein, J.; Sigger, F.; Straubinger, C.; Kremser, M.; Taniguchi, T.; Watanabe, K.; Wurstbauer, U.; Holleitner, A. W.; Kaniber, M.; Müller, K.; Finley, J. J., Direct exciton emission from atomically thin transition metal dichalcogenide heterostructures near the lifetime limit. *Sci. Rep.* **2017**, *7*, 12383.
45. Mueller, T.; Malic, E., Exciton physics and device application of two-dimensional transition metal dichalcogenide semiconductors. *npj. 2D Mater. Appl.* **2018**, *2*, 29.
46. Hanbicki, A. T.; Chuang, H. J.; Rosenberger, M. R.; Hellberg, C. S.; Sivaram, S. V.; McCreary, K. M.; Mazin, I. I.; Jonker, B. T., Double Indirect Interlayer Exciton in a MoSe₂/WSe₂ van der Waals Heterostructure. *ACS Nano* **2018**, *12*, 4719-4726.
47. Okada, M.; Kutana, A.; Kureishi, Y.; Kobayashi, Y.; Saito, Y.; Saito, T.; Watanabe, K.; Taniguchi, T.; Gupta, S.; Miyata, Y.; Yakobson, B. I.; Shinohara, H.; Kitaura, R., Direct and Indirect Interlayer Excitons in a van der Waals Heterostructure of hBN/WS₂/MoS₂/hBN. *ACS Nano* **2018**, *12*, 2498-2505.
48. Xiao, D.; Liu, G. B.; Feng, W. X.; Xu, X. D.; Yao, W., Coupled Spin and Valley Physics in Monolayers of MoS₂ and Other Group-VI Dichalcogenides. *Phys. Rev. Lett.* **2012**, *108*, 196802.
49. Ciarrocchi, A.; Unuchek, D.; Avsar, A.; Watanabe, K.; Taniguchi, T.; Kis, A., Polarization switching and electrical control of interlayer excitons in two-dimensional van der Waals heterostructures. *Nat. Photonics* **2019**, *13*, 131-136.
50. Stier, A. V.; McCreary, K. M.; Jonker, B. T.; Kono, J.; Crooker, S. A., Exciton diamagnetic shifts and valley Zeeman effects in monolayer WS₂ and MoS₂ to 65 Tesla. *Nat. Commun.* **2016**, *7*, 10643.
51. Nagler, P.; Ballottin, M. V.; Mitioglu, A. A.; Durnev, M. V.; Taniguchi, T.; Watanabe, K.; Chernikov, A.; Schüller, C.; Glazov, M. M.; Christianen, P. C. M.; Korn, T., Zeeman Splitting and

Inverted Polarization of Biexciton Emission in Monolayer WS₂. *Phys. Rev. Lett.* **2018**, 121, 057402.

52. Zipfel, J.; Holler, J.; Mitioglu, A. A.; Ballottin, M. V.; Nagler, P.; Stier, A. V.; Taniguchi, T.; Watanabe, K.; Crooker, S. A.; Christianen, P. C. M.; Korn, T.; Chernikov, A., Spatial extent of the excited exciton states in WS₂ monolayers from diamagnetic shifts. *Phys. Rev. B* **2018**, 98, 075438.

53. Xi, J.; Zhao, T.; Wang, D.; Shuai, Z., Tunable Electronic Properties of Two-Dimensional Transition Metal Dichalcogenide Alloys: A First-Principles Prediction. *J. Phys. Chem. Lett.* **2014**, 5, 285-291.

54. Li, Y. L.; Ludwig, J.; Low, T.; Chernikov, A.; Cui, X.; Arefe, G.; Kim, Y. D.; van der Zande, A. M.; Rigosi, A.; Hill, H. M.; Kim, S. H.; Hone, J.; Li, Z. Q.; Smirnov, D.; Heinz, T. F., Valley Splitting and Polarization by the Zeeman Effect in Monolayer MoSe₂. *Phys. Rev. Lett.* **2014**, 113, 266804.

55. Borghardt, S.; Tu, J. S.; Winkler, F.; Schubert, J.; Zander, W.; Leosson, K.; Kardynal, B. E., Engineering of optical and electronic band gaps in transition metal dichalcogenide monolayers through external dielectric screening. *Phys. Rev. Mater.* **2017**, 1, 054001.

56. MacNeill, D.; Heikes, C.; Mak, K. F.; Anderson, Z.; Kormanyos, A.; Zolyomi, V.; Park, J.; Ralph, D. C., Breaking of Valley Degeneracy by Magnetic Field in Monolayer MoSe₂. *Phys. Rev. Lett.* **2015**, 114, 037401.

57. Wang, Z. F.; Mak, K. F.; Shan, J., Strongly Interaction-Enhanced Valley Magnetic Response in Monolayer WSe₂. *Phys. Rev. Lett.* **2018**, 120, 066402.

58. Srivastava, A.; Sidler, M.; Allain, A. V.; Lembke, D. S.; Kis, A.; Imamoglu, A., Valley Zeeman effect in elementary optical excitations of monolayer WSe₂. *Nat. Phys.* **2015**, 11, 141-147.

59. Qiu, C. Y.; Shen, X. N.; Cao, B. C.; Cong, C. X.; Saito, R.; Yu, J. J.; Dresselhaus, M. S.;

Yu, T., Strong magnetophonon resonance induced triple G-mode splitting in graphene on graphite probed by micromagneto Raman spectroscopy. *Phys. Rev. B* **2013**, 88, 165407.

60. Kresse, G.; Furthmuller, J., Efficiency of ab-initio total energy calculations for metals and semiconductors using a plane-wave basis set. *Comp. Mater. Sci.* **1996**, 6, 15-50.

61. Li, J. C.; Kang, J. Y., Band engineering in $\text{Al}_{0.5}\text{Ga}_{0.5}\text{N}/\text{GaN}$ superlattice by modulating Mg dopant. *Appl. Phys. Lett.* **2007**, 91, 152106.

62. Lin, W.; Li, S. P.; Kang, J. Y., Polarization effects on quantum levels in InN/GaN quantum wells. *Nanotechnology* **2009**, 20, 485204.